

Infringements in Application of Community Law: Some Problems and (Im)possible Solutions

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Abstract

On the basis of Case C-508/03 Commission v. United Kingdom [2006] ECR I-3969 this article shows some problems brought by an infringement procedure, concerning a particular case of misapplication of EC law by Member State's public authorities. Firstly, some individuals can benefit from the infringement. How is their legal position affected by the ECJ's judgment? Secondly, is it appropriate for the Commission to bring the action to the ECJ before the case has been finally settled on the national level? Thirdly, are these individuals properly represented before the Court?

I Introduction*

The judgment Case C-508/03 delivered in an infringement procedure against the United Kingdom concerned Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA).¹ Such an assessment, according to the Commission's application, had not been carried out in respect of some development consents granted by the UK's competent authorities. Two developers wanted to build leisure and retail facilities in London, White City and Crystal Palace. The consents were granted at an initial planning stage, without an EIA. At the same time, however, the authorities reserved some matters for a later stage. When they were deciding on these reserved matters, they had considered that the EIA could indeed have been required. However, as a matter of the UK legislation, this was no more possible and the authorities had to issue their consents without the assessment.

In this case the Commission went beyond an action concerning incorrect transposition of the EIA directives into UK law.² The Commission

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¹ Particularly Council Directive 85/337/EEC of 27 June 1985 on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment, OJ 1985 L 175/40, as amended. Reference to the UK legislation is provided in the ECJ's judgment.

² I will leave the issue of incorrect transposition of the EIA directives into UK legislation, which did not allow carrying out an EIA at later stages of the consent procedure without closer analysis. With reference to its previous decision in *Wells*, the Court held in paras. 95-109 of its judgment that such a limitation is contrary to the EIA directives. See Case C-201/02 *Wells* [2004] ECR I-723, particularly para. 52.

further sought a declaration from the ECJ that when the London authorities considered an EIA unnecessary at the initial stage of the consent procedure (when it was still possible to require its carrying out), they failed to apply rules concerning EIA correctly. Throughout the comment I will call this “infringement in application”.

Such kind of infringement procedure will cover the phases of implementation of Community law when Community rules have already been transposed into national laws and the State has already created institutional framework for their proper application, but the application itself or enforcement of the relevant rules for some reason violates Community law.³ I will focus on three specific problems, which this kind of infringement procedure can bring.

Firstly, in an infringement procedure, which concerns a particular case of misapplication of EC law by Member State’s institution, some individuals can benefit from the infringement. In our case for example, these are the developers having the consents in their hands. How is their legal position affected by the ECJ’s judgment? Secondly, is it appropriate for the Commission to bring the action to the ECJ before the case has been finally settled on the national level? Thirdly, and finally, if the judgment delivered in an infringement procedure has direct consequences for individuals involved in the infringement, are these individuals properly represented before the Court?

2 Infringements in Application and the Position of Individuals Affected

How to comply with ECJ judgments?

In its defence, the UK government presented an interesting argument, which shows how Community law penetrates to national legal orders not only to the benefit of individuals, but potentially to their detriment as well. The UK pleaded that “in view of the considerable length of time that [had] passed since the planning permissions at issue were granted, the action for failure to fulfil obligations offend[ed] against the principle of legal certainty and undermin[ed] the legitimate expectations which developers [had derived] from acquired rights”.⁴ The Court admitted that “the principles of legal certainty and of the protection of legitimate expectations require the withdrawal of an unlawful measure to occur within a reasonable time and regard must be had to how far the person concerned might have been

³ For different stages of implementation of Community law see J.H. Jans, R. de Lange, S. Prechal and R.J.G.M. Widdershoven, *Europeanisation of Public Law* (Europa Law Publishing, Groningen 2007) at 13-18.

⁴ Judgment, para. 67.

led to rely on the lawfulness of the measure”.⁵ However, it added that “the fact remains that such withdrawal is, in principle, permitted”.⁶ Finally, the Court concluded:

‘A Member State cannot therefore rely on legal certainty and legitimate expectations derived by developers from acquired rights in order to prevent the Commission from bringing an action seeking an objective finding that the Member State has failed to fulfil its obligations under Directive 85/337 with regard to assessment of the effects of certain projects on the environment.’⁷

So long as the judgment in an infringement case remains an objective finding of a breach of Community law limited to the relationship between a Member State and the Community, it remains unproblematic. However, one must think further about the consequences of such a judgment.

As the Court stated in another recent judgment in *Commission v. Germany*, “[p]ursuant to Article 228(1) EC, the Member State concerned is required to take the measures necessary to comply with the judgment of the Court”.⁸ Since *Commission v. France*⁹ it has been clear that the Court can order both financial penalties provided for by Article 228(2) EC – lump sum covering the period between the first judgment given in a procedure according to Article 226 EC and the second judgment according to Article 228 EC condemning the State for not complying with the former and motivating this State to comply as soon as possible.¹⁰

Should it therefore mean that the UK authorities are required to withdraw the consents in order to fulfil the obligations stemming from the judgment of the Court finding these consents in breach of Community law? Should they do so regardless of the position of those who have based their actions on these consents and had legitimate expectations that their actions were lawful?

As one can observe from some other recent cases, the Court is meeting conflicts between the requirements of effectiveness of Community law on the one hand and legal certainty on the other more and more often. Most recently the Court held in *Lucchini Siderurgica* that

‘Community law precludes the application of a provision of national law, [...], which seeks to lay down the principle of *res judicata* in so far as the applica-

⁵ Judgment, para. 68.

⁶ *Ibid.*

⁷ Judgment, para. 69.

⁸ Case C-503/04 *Commission v. Germany*, nyr.

⁹ Case C-304/02 *Commission v. France* [2005] ECR I-6263.

¹⁰ See P. Wennerås, ‘A New Dawn for Commission Enforcement under Articles 226 and 228 EC: General and Persistent (GAP) Infringements, Lump Sums and Penalty Payments’, (2006) 43 *CML Rev* 31 at 50-61 for a closer analysis of the judgment.

tion of that provision prevents the recovery of State aid granted in breach of Community law which has been found to be incompatible with the common market in a decision of the Commission which has become final.”¹¹

It is to be seen how far the Court intended such a bold statement to be applicable, given the very specific factual circumstances of the case.¹² However, it seems possible that the Court will not stop short before asking the Member States for withdrawing administrative decisions in order to comply with its judgments. Another recent case seems to give hints of what its approach can be.

In *Commission v. Germany*,¹³ the Commission required Germany to ensure rescission of contracts for the collection of waste water and of a contract for waste disposal concluded between the City of Brunswick and a private company in breach of Directive 89/665,¹⁴ which the Court found in its previous judgment delivered in Article 226 EC procedure.¹⁵ Germany pleaded, supported by some other governments, that the directive allowed to provide in the national legislation that after the conclusion of a contract following the award of a public contract, the bringing of an action can give rise only to an award of damages and, thus, to exclude any possibility of rescission of that contract. This according to Germany precluded the possibility of finding of failure to fulfil obligations within the meaning of Article 226 EC with regard to such a contract entailing the obligation to rescind it. It further supported this conclusion, amongst other things, by reference to the principles of legal certainty and of the protection of legitimate expectations, the principle *pacta sunt servanda* and the fundamental right to property.¹⁶

The Court was not persuaded. The provision of the directive relied upon by the governments “[could not] be regarded also as regulating the relations between a Member State and the Community in the context of Articles 226 EC and 228 EC.”¹⁷ As regards the general principles of law referred to by the governments, the Court held that

‘even if it were to be accepted that [they] could be used against the contracting authority by the other party to the contract in the event of rescission, Member States cannot rely thereon to justify the non-implementation of a judgment

¹¹ Case C-119/05 *Lucchini Siderurgica*, nyr.

¹² See case comment, P. Bříza, ‘ECJ case *Lucchini SpA* – is there anything left of res judicata principle?’, forthcoming in (2008) *CJQ*.

¹³ Op. cit. n. 8.

¹⁴ Council Directive 89/665/EEC of 21 December 1989 on the coordination of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions relating to the application of review procedures to the award of public supply and public works contracts, OJ 1989 L 395/33.

¹⁵ Joined Cases C-20/01 and C-28/01 *Commission v. Germany* [2003] ECR I-3609.

¹⁶ *Commission v. Germany*, op. cit. n. 8, para. 31.

¹⁷ *Ibid*, para. 35.

establishing a failure to fulfil obligations under Article 226 EC and thereby evade their own liability under Community law.¹⁸

But how can a Member State fulfil its obligations, if the Court accepted that a private party could prevent rescission of the contract by reference to the general principles of law? Similarly in the case of the UK and planning permissions issued without EIA, the Court excludes the possibility of the Member State to rely on the principle of legal certainty and legitimate expectations derived by developers from acquired rights in order to prevent the Commission from bringing an action in infringement. The only way for a Member State to avoid financial penalties for not fulfilling Court's judgments seems to ignore these principles and to rescind contracts concluded in breach of the rules concerning public procurement, as was the German case,¹⁹ or to withdraw developers' permissions, as it is the case of the UK we analyse here.²⁰

It seems that the Court ignores the consequences of its findings in cases of infringement for legal relations established on the domestic level, therefore outside the relationship between the Community and a Member State. This is particularly pertinent in case of infringements in application, where it is in their very nature that some existing legal relationships are concerned. The Court seems to consider that it is always possible to remedy the breach of Community law and that it will not be satisfied with a mere financial reparation.

Different approach in preliminary rulings

The Court's approach is different when it decides on referrals from national courts. In *Wells*,²¹ another case where a mining permission was granted without EIA, the Court considered the possibilities of remedying the failure to carry out an EIA. These possibilities were, "subject to the limits laid down by the principle of procedural autonomy of the Member States, the revocation or suspension of a consent already granted, in order to carry out an [EIA]"²² and "[making] good any harm caused by the failure to carry out an environmental impact assessment".²³ However, it left for

¹⁸ *Ibid*, para. 36.

¹⁹ It is fair to add, however, that the German government had found the way how to rescind the contracts, as required by the Court, even before the Commission lodged its action.

²⁰ There is no space to analyse different approaches of national legal systems to revoking unlawful administrative decisions. While in English law it seems to be almost always possible, French law is much more restrictive and imposes time limitation on such a possibility. See S.J. Schönberg, 'Legal Certainty and Revocation of Administrative Decisions: A Comparative Study of English, French, and EC Law', (1999-2000) 19 *YEL* 257 at 281-294.

²¹ *Wells*, *op. cit.* n. 2.

²² *Wells*, *op. cit.* n. 2, para. 65.

²³ *Ibid*, para. 66.

‘the national court to determine whether it is possible under domestic law for a consent already granted to be revoked or suspended in order to subject the project in question to an assessment of its environmental effects, in accordance with the requirements of Directive 85/337, or alternatively, if the individual so agrees, whether it is possible for the latter to claim compensation for the harm suffered.’²⁴

As it is obvious, the choice of the proper remedy is left for national courts, which can give regard to the provisions of domestic law.

Similarly in *i-21 Germany and Arcor*²⁵ the Court subjected a duty to re-open final administrative decisions issued contrary to Community law to the limits provided by national law (complying with the requirements of the principle of effectiveness and equivalence), not to mention *Kühne & Heitz*,²⁶ where the Court set even stricter conditions for such a reopening.²⁷ However, when it comes to the Member States and their duty to fulfil their obligations in order to avoid infringement procedure against them, the Court’s approach differs.

More scope for balancing on a case-by-case basis?

Following the logic of *Commission v. Germany*,²⁸ compensation of the harm does not preclude an infringement action, if the domestic law does not allow revoking or suspending the consent already granted. It seems that the Member States are left in a trap: in order to avoid financial sanctions, they must breach general principles, such as protection of legitimate expectations or legal certainty, which protect individuals.

It could be argued that this is exactly what the Court intends: the Member State can compensate for a loss caused to an individual from whom a favourable administrative decision has been withdrawn in breach of his legitimate expectations in order to comply with the ECJ’s judgment. It is questionable, however, that unlawfulness can be remedied by another unlawfulness in a State based on the rule of law. How the Court should proceed, then?

The Court should take into account the actual possibility of a Member State to comply with Article 226 EC judgment, when deciding on an action pursued by the Commission according to Article 228 EC. It seems that

²⁴ Ibid, para. 69.

²⁵ Joined Cases C-392/04 and C-422/04 *i-21 Germany and Arcor* [2006] ECR I-8559. See the case analysis by Jans & Marseille elsewhere (p. 75-86) in this volume of *REALaw*.

²⁶ Case C-453/00 *Kühne & Heitz* [2004] ECR I-837. See case comment by Roberto Caranta, (2005) 42 *CML Rev* 179.

²⁷ Although, it is questionable to what extent is *Kühne & Heitz* good law after *i-21 Germany and Arcor*, and whether both these judgments hold after the Court’s decision in *Lucchini Siderurgica*, cited in n. 11.

²⁸ Cited in n. 8.

while a Member State cannot indeed plead that legal certainty of individuals prevents the Court from *finding* a breach of Community law (as the Court held in response to the UK's argument in our commented case²⁹), it should be possible for a Member State to assert that it cannot nevertheless *remedy this breach completely* by committing another breach, this time concerning individuals and the general principles of law that protect them. In a possible scenario based on the commented case, the UK should be allowed to leave the outline planning consents untouched, if they cannot be revoked without breaching developers' rights acquired in good faith.

This would reflect a more balancing approach, which the Court itself takes in cases concerning revocation of unlawful administrative decisions. In some instances the revocation is barred, depending also on the nature of the decision.³⁰ The Court considers first, recipient's legitimate expectation that the decision finally settled the matter, second, how third parties will be affected if the unlawful decision is allowed to stand, and third, the time which has lapsed. Affected person's interests are being balanced against the principle of legality of administrative decision.³¹ The same should apply when compliance with EC law would require revocation of administrative decisions issued in breach of EC law and the Member States should have some scope to protect individuals' trust in law and its institutions. They should therefore be able, within the framework of the "second" infringement procedure according to Article 228 EC, to plead protection of the principles of legal certainty and irrevocability of certain administrative decision in defence of their non-compliance with ECJ's judgments delivered in the "first" infringement procedure according to Article 226 EC, contrary to what *Commission v. Germany* suggests now.

3 The Role of the National Institutional System

Waiting for the final determination of the case on the national level?

The UK government presented another interesting argument to the Court, claiming that it is for its own courts to determine whether the competent authorities incorrectly concluded that EIA had not been necessary. The Court replied briefly that

'the fact that proceedings have been brought before a national court to challenge the decision of a competent authority which is the subject of an action for failure to fulfil obligations and the decision of that court cannot affect the admissibility of the action for failure to fulfil obligations brought by the

²⁹ See n. 7.

³⁰ On the classification see Schönberg, *op. cit.* n. 20 at 258-259.

³¹ See Schönberg, *op. cit.* n. 20 at 291-293.

Commission. The existence of the remedies available through the national courts cannot prejudice the bringing of an action under Article 226 EC, since the two procedures have different objectives and effects.³²

At first reading this seems unproblematic; however, also here the peculiar nature of infringements in application brings some interesting questions.

The Court's approach that does not distinguish between different Member States' institutions responsible for breaches of Community law³³ sometimes leads to intriguing questions: is it the legislator, who violated Community law by enacting a provision contrary to Community law (or by failing to implement Community obligations)? Or is it an administrative authority, which applied these laws contrary to Community law in spite of the Court's judgment requiring it to apply Community law directly?³⁴ Or, finally, should the courts be blamed for not having provided remedies for these breaches?³⁵

One could imagine, especially after the judgment in *Commission v. Italy*,³⁶ that the Court can leave more responsibility in the hands of national courts and intervene only after these institutions have failed to apply Community law properly. In *Commission v. Italy* the Court came close to condemning for the first time a Member State for infringements of Community law committed by its courts. Finally, however, it found that relevant national legislation was insufficiently clear and left scope for judicial misconstruction. The blame was therefore put on the legislator instead of on the judiciary.³⁷ Some members of the Court nevertheless read the judgment differently as suggesting that the Court is indeed willing to find infringements of Community law entailing judicial decisions. Advocate General Colomer opined that

³² Judgment, para. 71.

³³ In particular with regard to the division of powers between courts and other institutions see Opinion of AG Geelhoed in Case C-129/00 *Commission v. Italy* [2003] ECR I-14637, para. 53 and the case law cited therein.

³⁴ See Case 103/88 *Fratelli Costanzo* [1989] ECR I839.

³⁵ See G. Anagnostaras, 'The Allocation of Responsibility in State Liability Actions for Breach of Community Law: A Modern Gordian Knot', (2001) 26 *EL Rev* 139 in relation to liability of Member States for damages caused to individuals.

³⁶ Case C-129/00 *Commission v. Italy* [2003] ECR I-14637.

³⁷ See J. Komárek, 'Federal Elements in the Community Judicial System – Building Coherence in the Community Legal Order', (2005) 42 *CML Rev* 9 at 25. See also the operative part of the judgment which states: "by failing to amend [relevant provision of national law], which is construed and applied by the administrative authorities and a substantial proportion of the courts, including the [Italian Supreme Court of Cassation], in such a way that the exercise of the right to repayment of charges levied in breach of Community rules is made excessively difficult for the taxpayer, the Italian Republic has failed to fulfil its obligations under the EC Treaty" (my emphasis).

‘the Court found [in *Commission v. Italy*] that the national provision itself was neutral but held that the manner in which it was construed and applied by the administrative authorities and a substantial proportion of the courts, including the [Italian Supreme Court of Cassation], amounted to an infringement of Community law.’³⁸

Under Colomer’s reading of *Commission v. Italy* it would be possible for the Court to go even further and to accept the UK’s argument that its infringement of Community law can still be remedied by its own courts. This is especially the case when the Court deals with infringement in application: it is possible to say that in such cases it should be the whole institutional system of the State that is to have its say and only if this system as a whole fails, the Court can condemn the State for an infringement. The UK government could try to put the argument differently: not as a question of jurisdiction of the Court, but as a question of timing the Commission’s action.³⁹ The government’s argument could be that until the case is finally determined on the national level, it is not possible for the Commission to bring an infringement action concerning that particular case. Another consideration, concerning the burden of proof on the part of the Commission, can support this view.

The problem of the burden of proof

When the Commission argued that the London authorities should have carried out an EIA already at the initial stage of the consent procedure, it did not submit any substantive evidence that the projects were likely to have significant effects on the environment, to make the assessment necessary. It merely stated the planned scale and size of the projects in question created a presumption that an assessment had been necessary. On the other hand, the UK government argued that the London authorities had a number of reports at their disposal and provided for public consultation before concluding that the assessment would not be made.

The issue concerned the burden of proof, which is much harder to bear for the Commission in cases concerning infringement in application. As is well known, the Commission has very limited means to monitor actual compliance with Community law in the Member States and must to a great extent rely on individual complaints.⁴⁰ After all, also this infringement procedure was initiated after such a complaint.

³⁸ Opinion of AG Colmer in Case C-490/04 *Commission v. Germany*, nyr, para. 73. See also his Opinion in Joined Cases C-338/04, C-359/04 and C-360/04 *Placanica*, nyr, para. 83.

³⁹ However, given the way in which the Court sometimes deals with parties’ arguments in its judgments, it is possible that the UK pled something slightly different than the judgment suggests.

⁴⁰ See Wennerås, op. cit. n. 10 at 31-32.

Already in *Commission v. Ireland*⁴¹ the ECJ had lightened the requirement on the part of the Commission in a way that according to some “[came] close to a reversal of the burden of proof [...] which to some extent [went] at the expense of Member States’ judicial protection”.⁴² In the commented case the Court reiterated its holding in *Commission v. Ireland*:

‘[W]here the Commission has adduced sufficient evidence of certain matters in the territory of the defendant Member State, it is incumbent on the latter to challenge in substance and in detail the information produced and the consequences flowing therefrom.’⁴³

However, the Court also stressed that “the Commission must furnish at least some evidence of the effects that the project in question is likely to have on the environment”.⁴⁴ The general assertions of the Commission were not sufficient in that respect: “[The Commission] cannot merely rely on presumptions that large-scale projects are automatically likely to have significant effects on the environment without establishing, on the basis of at least some specific evidence, that the competent authorities made a manifest error of assessment.”⁴⁵ The Court reproved the Commission for not attempting to refute the UK’s arguments, backed up by analytical documents and materials, which had left the Court unable to assess whether the competent authorities did in fact exceed the limits of their discretion.⁴⁶ It therefore dismissed the application in that respect.

It is possible to imagine that if the Commission had waited for the very end of the procedures simultaneously running before the UK courts, it could have had the evidence presented there at its disposal and could have supported its case by analytical documents and materials, as required by the Court. Should the Commission’s practice of “an early action” against the Member States (approved by the Court) therefore be criticized? The following will show that on the balance, it is not the case.

Defending the Court’s approach: the need for effective enforcement

The Court’s solution can nevertheless be defended on various grounds. First, it can be argued that condemning national courts for their breaches of Community law is not the best way of protecting the image of cooperative relationship in the European judicial system (whatever the reality of this cooperation is).⁴⁷ This will nevertheless not be the strongest of the argu-

⁴¹ Case C-494/01 *Commission v. Ireland* [2005] ECR I-3331.

⁴² Wennerås, op. cit. n. 10 at 41.

⁴³ Judgment, para. 80.

⁴⁴ Judgment, para. 78.

⁴⁵ Judgment, para. 92.

⁴⁶ See Judgment, para. 93.

⁴⁷ See Komárek, op. cit. 37 at 21-26.

ments, because the Court can always do what it did in *Commission v. Italy*: condemn the State without specifying which of its institutions was finally responsible and thus avoid singling out its judicial partners in the Member States.

Another consideration in support of the Court's approach is more persuasive: if the Commission had to wait with its action against the Member State until the case is conclusively determined on the national level, it would be much harder to remedy the breach in case the Court would have eventually found it. This would be even more true if the Court accepts protection of individuals' acquired rights and the principle of legal certainty as a possible Member State's defence, as the preceding part of this comment suggested.

As regards the argument concerning the better availability of evidence produced in the national proceedings, it can be said that the Court accepts e.g. reports produced by NGOs, which can disprove governments' assertions.⁴⁸

On the balance, therefore, the Commission's "early action" seems justified. Still, there is another element of the cases of infringement in application, which makes them problematic. It concerns the right to be heard of those affected by the infringement.

4 Division of Powers among European Courts and the Right to be Heard of an Individual Affected

The Court had an opportunity to adjudicate on the case of EIA omitted by London authorities in another case, this time a preliminary reference from the House of Lords. As in the infringement case against the UK, the Court had to decide on compatibility of the UK legislation with the EIA directives. In the judgment, which was delivered the same day as in the commented case it stated that

'it is [...] the task of the national court to verify whether the outline planning permission and decision approving reserved matters which are at issue in the main proceedings constitute, as a whole, a 'development consent' for the purposes of Directive 85/337 (see, in this connection, the judgment delivered today in [*Commission v United Kingdom*], paragraphs 101 and 102).⁴⁹

However, as the opinion of Lord Hope of Craighead suggests, there was very little for that court to "verify":

⁴⁸ See e.g. Case C-235/04 *Commission v. Spain*, nyr, where the Commission relied on an ornithological list produced by the Spanish Ornithological Society. The Court dismissed the Spanish government's arguments as to its alleged unreliability caused by the source – an independent body, not supervised by the Commission.

⁴⁹ Case C-290/03 *Barker* [2006] ECR I-3949, para. 46.

‘In my opinion the answer to the question whether the outline planning permission and the decision to approve the reserved matters in this case constituted, as a whole, a “development consent” for the purposes of the Directive is now plain. It is conveniently set out in the [ECJ]’s judgment in [Commission v United Kingdom], paras 101-102. [The developers] were told in [the] outline planning permission that they were not entitled to proceed with any development until details relating to the reserved matters had been submitted to and approved by the local planning authority. That being so, the decisions to grant outline planning permission and to approve the reserved matters must be considered to constitute, as a whole, a multi-stage development consent for the purposes of the Directive.’⁵⁰

So even if the ECJ formally reserves some matters for the national court to decide, in fact it is this Court that makes the principal determination. The point is that this determination is argued outside the national proceedings without the parties (whose rights can be directly or indirectly affected) being represented there. This is another problematic element of infringements in application, which is, however, due to the structural limitations of the infringement procedure, hardly reparable.

5 Conclusion

The comment examined some of the problematic elements of infringements entailing a concrete case of misapplication of Community law by national authorities, which at the same time concerns individuals. It suggested that once these infringements are being dealt with before the ECJ, it could be no more possible to treat the infringement as concerning only the Member State and the Community. Individuals and their rights must be taken into account as well. It should not be controversial, if Community law truly forms part of individuals’ legal heritage.⁵¹

The question remains whether the rights of individuals based on Community law are taken seriously only when they serve as instruments to enforce Community law in the Member States, or, whether they stand also in the case when they limit the possibilities of the Member States to remedy their breaches of Community law. The answer to this question should be searched for constantly.

⁵⁰ Regina (*Barker*) v. Bromley London Borough Council (Secretary of State for Communities and Local Government, intervener), [2006] 3 WLR 1209 at 1219.

⁵¹ Case 26/62 *Van Gend en Loos* [1963] ECR I at 12.